

Application of non-destructive examination for industrial inspection and conformity assessment under EN ISO/IEC 17020:2012

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ABSTRACT

In 2012 a new version of ISO/IEC 17020 “Conformity assessment - Requirements for the operation of various types of bodies performing inspection” was published and subsequently adopted by CEN and CENELEC as a European Standard. A number of requirements and clauses have been reviewed in this new version of the standard, which is supplemented by guideline documents EA 05/01 and EA 04/15 of the European Cooperation for Accreditation, by various clauses and requirements of European Union directives, most notably 97/23/EEC (PED) and 305/2011 (CPR), and by international and European standards. This paper examines the current situation regarding application of NDT/NDE in initial inspection and certification of industrial equipment for the European market and periodic inspections under the requirements of these documents. It also examines the effects of these documents on accredited and notified inspection bodies in terms of organization structure and personnel certification requirements.

Keywords: Inspection Bodies, NDT metrology, NDT personnel certification

1 Introduction

This review paper investigates the requirements imposed to inspection bodies operating in the European Union due to their involvement in performing non-destructive examination / non-destructive testing (NDE/NDT) and/or accepting or rejecting products based on NDE/NDT results. The issues addressed in this paper have been investigated in a number of publications ^{[8], [9]} with reference to the previous versions of the relevant standards.

2 Standardization issues

Inspection Bodies (IB) in the European Union, especially when involved in statutory inspections, operate according to ISO/IEC 17020, successor standard of EN 45004, under the general requirements of Regulation 765/2008.^[1] In 2012 a new edition of ISO/IEC 17020 was published and subsequently adopted by CEN and CENELEC as a European Standard. A number of requirements and clauses have been reviewed in this new edition of

the standard, which is much more detailed than the previous edition. Activities of IB related to products covered by New Approach European directives and regulations are closely linked with those of Notified Certification Bodies operating under ISO/IEC 17065. In most such cases the same organization is responsible for certification, most of inspection and part of testing.

At the same time, accreditation bodies enforce additional requirements which are stated in various EA and IAF guidelines, of which IAF/ILAC-A4, EA 05/01^[2]^[3] and, especially, EA 04/15^[4] are applicable in inspections involving NDT. Accreditation bodies may be even more prescriptive in the implementation of specific clauses of ISO/IEC 17020.

Regarding Non-destructive testing, in June 2012 we were glad to finally see the merging of EN 473 and ISO 9712 in a single standard, EN ISO 9712:2012, this being the result of harmonization activities which lasted for approximately two decades.^[5] In July 2012 we also had the release of the new version of EN ISO/IEC 17024:2012, which indirectly affects NDT personnel certification, but is peripheral to the content of this paper.^[6]

We are also in the middle of the process of introduction of new regulation 305/2011 (CPR – Construction Products Regulation), which repeals Directive 89/106/EEC (CPD). The new regulation has the interesting feature to prescribe use of European harmonized standards for all conformity assessment, including welding and NDT.

3 EN ISO/IEC 17020:2012 requirements

3.1 Personnel §6.1

ISO/IEC 17020 requires the inspectors of the inspection body be capable of:

- Testing products, processes and, in some cases, personnel e.g. approval of welders (PED Appendix I, 3.1.2).
- Determining conformity with specific requirements on the basis of professional judgment.

Employment (hiring and training) of suitable inspectors tends to be one of the main expenses of an IB. As can be concluded from paragraphs 4, 5 and 6 of this paper, in many sectors, inspectors must have the capability to conduct NDT testing and/or assess NDT reports. In addition, more specialized expertise is required in some cases, to the Level 3 of ISO 9712 or even beyond that (paragraph 7).

ISO/IEC 17020 is also very specific about training of inspectors, including initial and continuing training (§6.1.6). This training can add an additional expense to the inspection body.

3.2 Facilities and equipment §6.2

With the exception of major certification and inspection bodies, which operate their own NDT laboratories, an inspection body needs limited facilities for storage, small scale maintenance and simple in-house calibration of measuring equipment, consumables etc. Additional space may be required for storage of samples and specimens, a usual solution being to dispose off of them within weeks or, at most, at the end of a specific contract.

Normally radiography, if it is the responsibility of the IB, it is subcontracted to a specialized organization. It is up to the IB to decide if it gets involved in extensive applications of other NDT methods, for example ultrasonic testing of large oil storage tanks, or prefers to subcontract them; the decision is based mainly on business management factors.

While ISO/IEC 17020 does not specify a retention time for records, for various reasons an inspection body may choose to retain inspection records indefinitely (or for very long periods) and other records (personnel training etc) for years. Acceptable (safe and secure) storage facilities may be a problem for smaller inspection bodies.

3.3 Inspection methods and procedures

In many cases the requirements for inspection are laid down in codes and standards. Usually these texts are fairly prescriptive and there is little need for interpretation. In some cases, however, the IB has to make decisions about issues not covered explicitly or with enough detail in the relevant standard.

In other cases the IB is working as or for a third-party organization for non-statutory inspections. In these cases some or most requirements are contained in technical appendices of contract documents, while at the same time the contract has general requirements to codes and standards. In these cases the IB faces the difficult tasks to sort out any differences between contract documents and standards.

In both cases stated above, the IB must have well defined inspections methods. These methods usually involve NDT, almost always visual testing, and other methods according to the nature of the inspection. Permanent staff, temporary staff and subcontractors involved in inspection should use the same methods. The methods and associated procedures can be of a permanent nature, when the field of application is wide and they are used frequently, or they can be very specific to one project or to the inspection of a single item.

When the methods involve NDT, a Level 3 person is needed to undertake the following activities:

- Approve of in-house procedures of the IB.
- Review of procedures developed or supplied by customers, especially in the case of third party inspections (§7.1.6).
- Interpret codes and standards, if needed.
- Identify training and certification requirements for NDT personnel, especially temporary or employed by subcontractors.
- Establish metrological parameters (precision-accuracy, GUM uncertainty, repeatability and reproducibility) of quantitative NDT techniques. This activity requires knowledge and skills beyond that of the standard ASNT and ISO 9712 Level 3 syllabus.

3.4 Subcontracting

Subcontracting involves three distinct cases:

- Subcontracting actual NDT to a specialized laboratory so that the IB confines itself to assessment (approval/rejection decision) based on reports.
- Subcontracting part of the inspection (testing and assessment) process, this is normally within the capabilities of the IB.
- Using specialist assessment resources available from specialist businesses, e.g. finite elements analysis, complicated assessment of fitness-for-service (API 579) etc.

ISO/IEC 17020, §6.3, covers various aspects of subcontracting, the most important clause being that “*the responsibility for any determination of conformity... shall remain with the inspection body*” (§6.3.2).

IAF/ILAC-A4 requires the IB to be able to evaluate the competence of the subcontractor using criteria of ISO/IEC 17020 or ISO/IEC 17025, as appropriate, through a second-part assessment. As accreditation bodies interpret this clause in a very narrow sense, IB tend to adopt the policy to use only accredited subcontractors when available, and especially for contracts covered by their accreditation.

4 Requirements for statutory inspections under EU rules

In general, European Regulations and Directive of the New Approach family do not impose specific requirements on issues related to NDT, with two exceptions, Directive 97/23/EEC and Regulation 305/2011/EU. In these cases the operation of the inspection body is closely connected with its operation as a certification body (Notified Body) or as a subcontractor of a certification body.

4.1 Directive 97/23/EEC (PED)

If the IB is involved in initial inspection of equipment covered by Directive 97/23/EEC (PED – Pressure Equipment Directive) and falling in categories III and IV, then certain special requirements apply. The Directive requires central independent certification of NDT personnel, however it does not enforce use of EN ISO 9712 (formerly EN 473), it just encourages it through the harmonized standards. Under PED no accreditation is required for the manufacturer’s NDT or DT laboratory or for the testing laboratory that *the manufacturer* may subcontract for NDT or DT (PED Guideline 6.9) ^[12].

If the PED modules C1, D, E, E1, H or H1 are used (meaning that the manufacturer has a quality system approved by the Notified Body), then almost all NDT responsibilities lie with the manufacturer and its subcontractors. In this case the Notified Body needs access to specialized NDT personnel as auditors and/or experts only during initial certification and surveillance activities.

If PED modules F or G are used in conjunction with harmonized standards, then, while NDT is still to be performed under the responsibility of the manufacturer, the inspection body is more actively involved in inspection activities. Its inspectors should be able to assess equipment based on NDT reports, to evaluate NDT procedures and to check the credentials of NDT personnel. Therefore the inspection body must employ inspectors certified at least to Level 2 and also have access to experts certified to Level 3.

Certification of IB inspectors to ISO 9712 is not required explicitly, provided that testing is performed by certified personnel of the other parties involved.

It is possible, and it does happen at times, that pressure equipment is designed and manufactured without use of the harmonized standards. Usually it is equipment designed and manufactured according to the ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code. In this case, ASME Section V, ASTM and ASNT requirements apply, with the additional requirement that NDT personnel shall be certified according to PED Appendix I, §3.1.3. Personnel certified under ASNT/ASME/ASTM standards may be approved by a recognized third party organization, if certification criteria equivalent to the harmonized standards have been met, and that the scope of certification is relevant to the testing of welds in pressure equipment (PED Guideline 6.13).^[12]

4.2 Regulation 305/2011 (CPR)

The new Regulation 305/2011 (CPR – Construction Products Regulation) prescribes use of harmonized standards (Article 17, §3) for all activities affecting product conformity, so prefabricated products in steel and aluminum (load bearing steel structures, steel tanks etc) shall be tested according to them, and the conformity shall be assessed and verified by a Notified Body (Annex V).

It is expected that many questions shall arise when Regulation 305/2011 enters into force in 2013 and is tried in actual cases of construction projects.

4.3 EN 1090-2

For steel construction, the applicable execution standard is EN 1090-1 and EN 1090-2.

EN 1090-2 in §2.5 contains normative references to CEN NDT standards, as of 2008-2009, including EN 473.

In §12.4.2 is specifies the extent and methodology for NDT of welds for execution classes 2, 3 and 4. These classes are linked to the requirements of Eurocode EN 1990, Appendix B.

4.4 EN 12952, EN 12953

EN 12952 (15 parts) is the harmonized standard covering the design, construction and inspection of water-tube steam generators. Inspection during construction is covered in part 6 of the standard, which was updated in 2011. NDT issues are covered in paragraphs 5 (for parent materials) and 9 (for testing and approval of welds).

Paragraph 5 is actually a redirection to §4.1.6 of EN 12952-2:2011. This is a list of applicable standards and acceptance levels for defects for steel plate (EN 10160), tubes and pipes (EN 10893-10), forged/rolled bars and cast steel products. Interestingly, EN 10160 explicitly specifies that ultrasonic testing of steel plates shall take place under the supervision of a EN 473 Level 3.

Paragraph 9 is much more detailed, as it contains specific requirements on the extent of inspection, the qualifications of personnel and the acceptance criteria with reference to ISO

6520 and ISO 5817. It directly refers to harmonized NDT standards which were current at the time of approval of this part of the standard.

Table A-1 shows the requirements for NDT personnel in the 2002 version of the standard and the changes in the 2011 version. Two notable items in this part are:

- There is no explicit requirement for all RT personnel to be certified to EN 473 (EN ISO 9712), the requirement applies only to the radiographic interpreter.
- UT inspection of welds must now be conducted by a Level 2, instead of “*under his direct supervision*”.

EN 12953 is the harmonized standard for shell boilers, including steam boilers and some large hot water boilers that fall outside the scope of Ecodesign (Directive 92/42/EEC etc) and operate at temperatures of over 110⁰C. At the time of writing this presentation, the 2002 edition of EN 12953-5 remains current. Table A-2 shows the requirements for NDT personnel in the current (2002) version of the standard.

4.5 EN 13445

Harmonized standard EN 13445 deals with requirements for design and manufacture of Unfired Pressure Vessels. Part 5 §6.6.3.7 requires that NDT personnel shall be qualified and certified to EN 473:2008 (except for VT for which personnel shall be qualified but not certified) at an appropriate level of competence.

Due to the wide variety of equipment and materials covered by EN 13445, four different “testing groups” are defined, with Group 1 having the most strict requirements, group 2 applying to the standard high quality products and group 3 to products where less NDT is applied at the expense of higher wall thickness. Group 4 is a special category for vessels which are only subjected to visual inspection and pressure testing, at the expense of a joint coefficient of only 0.7. Subcontracting of NDT activities by the manufacturer is covered in §7.3

4.6 EN 13480

This is the harmonized standard for industrial piping, and it also contains requirements for NDT in Part 5. Requirements are generally similar to other harmonized standards of the PED family and those in the 2002 version are listed in Table A-3.

5 Statutory in-service inspections under national regulations

In this case inspection bodies are more frequently required to perform non-destructive testing using their own personnel, while subcontracting to a specialized agency (accredited laboratory) when the extend of testing is very high or special requirements apply (radiography for example).^[13] Ultrasonic thickness measurement, visual testing using endoscopes, eddy current testing of tubes and electromagnetic testing of wire ropes are used for in-service inspections of pressure equipment and machinery (including lifting equipment), supplemented by the standard methods used for initial testing as required.

Inspection bodies are not normally involved in inspections of ships (this is the field of classification societies) and aircraft (normally performed by agencies authorized by the national authorities and also approved by second-parties, the manufacturer of the equipment).

As national regulations are not always very prescriptive for in-service inspections, the requirements of IAF and EA guidelines listed in paragraph 2 are used as assessment criteria by the accreditation bodies.

A lack of European standards in this field has led many industrial customers to request inspection according to API (API 510 and API 570) and EIGA testing codes *under accreditation*.

6 Non-statutory party inspections

These may be third party inspections or in-service inspections and are not regulated at European or national level. A wide variety of methods are used, either complete testing codes (API 510^[14], API 570^[15]), specific standardized methods (ASTM E1351^[16], ISO 3057^[17]) or in-house methodologies based on state of the art technologies^{[10], [11]}.

For example operators of thermal power stations may use EN 12952-4 “In-service boiler life expectancy calculations”, which is not a PED harmonized standard, for assessment of steam generators (especially steam superheaters and reheaters), or any other relevant code at their discretion.

In these contracts an IB is free to offer services outside to its scope of accreditation. It may use NDT personnel with any type of certification (within reason) and apply only good engineering practice to calibration and metrology. However, when it reports conformity to a code or standard, all clauses of this standard must be adhered to, unless explicitly excluded from the scope of work. In many cases these contracts in the industrial sector are based on US standards (ASME, API) and in a few cases in internal standards and procedures of the customer.

7 Metrological issues

Accreditation of inspection bodies and laboratories poses requirements for estimation of the metrological parameters of NDT methods. While ISO/IEC 17020:2012 dictates good management, handling and calibration of testing equipment (§6) and proper management of inspection methods and procedures (§6), its requirements are less strict than those of ISO/IEC 17025 §5.4.5 and §5.4.6. However, the accreditation bodies impose increasingly stricter requirements.

For example, for calibration:

- IAF/ILAC-A4:2004, §9.7b specifies: “*Where the calibrations are performed inhouse, traceability to national standards should be assured by using reference standards of measurement for which the inspection body holds a current calibration certificate or equivalent from a competent body. The certificate or*

equivalent should detail an uncertainty of measurement that is appropriate for the equipment that is to be calibrated from the reference standard...”.

- EA-4/15 in addition requires that: *“Where in-house calibration/verification methods are adopted, the organisation shall have the necessary resources consistent with the accuracy required, and with any standard specifications relevant to the calibration/verification concerned. Procedures for in-house calibrations and verifications shall be adequately documented and describe how to perform the calibration/verification... Records of all calibrations/verifications shall be documented and retained and shall include certificates providing evidence of traceability to national standards where required.”*
- ESYD KO_DIAKRIV in addition specifies that inspection bodies performing in-house calibration of their equipment, shall fulfill the requirements of ISO/IEC 17025 and IAF/ILAC-A4 and shall be assessed for this by an assessor trained to the requirements of ISO/IEC 17025.

For the calculation of uncertainty of the inspection methods in use, EA-4/15, §7, does recognize the issue but avoids giving guidance for the calculation. Inspection bodies shall be prepared for stricter requirements in the near future. Fortunately the issue is addressed by NATA (the National Association of Testing Authorities in Australia) in their Technical Note 35.^[7] This document establishes a methodology for calculation of the uncertainties of NDT inspection following the ISO GUM model.

8 Conclusions

The current and forthcoming European regulatory framework and the updated accreditation and inspection standards impose increasingly complex requirements to the inspection bodies. Inspection bodies must have a good internal quality management structure, so they can identify needs in human and material resources in advance and avoid costly mistakes due to underestimation of requirements. Properly trained (and possibly certified) NDT inspectors are required in many activities, while access to Level 3 services becomes a necessity in more complex contracts. The increasing pressure for estimation of metrological parameters requires access to specialists, as existing NDT training and certification schemes do not cover it in the extend required.

9 Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Mr. G. Nikolopoulos for his assistance in referencing this paper.

10 Appendix

Table A-1	
EN 12952-6:2002, §9.2	EN 12952-6:2011, §9.2
Personnel responsible for non-destructive testing, including interpretation, evaluation and reporting shall be certified in accordance with the general requirements of EN 473.	No change, reference to EN 473:2008

An exception to this requirement shall be made for visual examination of welds and final inspection of boilers, for which EN 473 is not applicable.	No change, reference to EN 473:2008
MPI shall be performed under the direct supervision of personnel qualified to level 2 of EN 473 as a minimum.	No change, reference to EN 473:2008
DPI shall be performed under the direct supervision of personnel qualified to level 2 of EN 473 as a minimum.	No change, reference to EN 473:2008
Ultrasonic inspection shall be performed under the direct supervision of personnel qualified to level 2 of EN 473 as a minimum	Ultrasonic inspection shall be performed by an operator qualified to level 2 of EN 473:2008 as a minimum for UT.
Radiographs shall be viewed by personnel qualified to level 2 of EN 473 as a minimum.	No change, reference to EN 473:2008
Visual examination shall be carried out by experienced personnel having sufficient knowledge in welding techniques, and a full comprehension of this standard, to identify and interpret imperfections that might occur at the surface of the weld and the HAZ.	No change

Table A-2	
EN 12953-5:2002, §5.2.2	
Personnel responsible for non-destructive testing, including interpretation, evaluation and reporting shall be certified in accordance with the general requirements of EN 473.	
An exception to this requirement shall be made for visual examination of welds and final inspection of boilers, for which EN 473 is not applicable. Visual examinations shall be in accordance with EN 970.	
Visual examination shall be carried out by experienced personnel having sufficient knowledge in welding techniques, and a full comprehension of this European Standard, to identify and interpret imperfections that might occur at the surface of the weld and the HAZ.	
Radiographs shall be viewed by personnel qualified to level 2 of EN 473 as a minimum.	
MPI, DPI and ultrasonic examination shall be performed under the direct supervision of personnel qualified to level 2 of EN 473 as a minimum.	

Table A-3	
EN 13480-5	
Testing shall be carried out by an individual certified to at least EN 473:2000, level 1, under the supervision of personnel certified to level 2 or level 3 who shall also be responsible for the evaluation of the results.	
Visual examination to EN 970 shall be performed and evaluated by an individual with sufficient knowledge and experience with the relevant standards and specifications. Certifications in accordance with EN 473 are not required.	
Ultrasonic testing shall be performed and evaluated by an individual certified to at least EN 473:2000, level 2.	

11 References

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